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Annotation

This article gives information about compound sentences in the English language. In this article it has several paragraphs, which give full data about this. It is based on what is sentences? What is the difference between compound and simple sentences? In this article, candidates can learn how to be a good learner and what is compound sentences. And candidates can learn how to use it?

Key words: compound sentences, simple sentences, complex-compound, subject, predicates, simple subject, complete subject, simple predicate, complete predicate.

Clause: A main clause (independent clause) contains a subject and a predicate and can be used alone Example: Houston plays baseball. Dependent Clause (Dependent Clause) contains a subject and a predicate, but is not a complete thought. Begins with a subordinating conjunction. Example Because we won the game

What is sentences?

Sentences must contain both a subject and a verb and must express a complete thought. The subject is the person or thing that performs the action. Verbs are actions. Verbs are also called predicates.

Subjects and Predicates: Subject – the subject that performs the action Example: Susie called her friend. Complex Subject – Multiple Subjects Example: Susie and Joanne skipped rope during their break. Predicate – Action Example: Josh swam a lap in the pool. Compound Predicate - Two or More Actions Example This weekend, Josh rode his bike and went ice skating.

Simple Subject & Complete Subject: Simple subject- just the subject, no descriptors Ex: The young students enjoyed the game. Complete subject- the subject and descriptors

Simple Predicate & Complete Predicate: Simple predicate- the verb or verb phrase. Ex. Many students cheered wildly. Ex. Jane will finish the test after school.

Complete predicate- the action word plus descriptors Ex. Many students cheered wildly. Ex. Jane will finish the test after school.Ex. The young students enjoyed the game.

Simple Sentences:A simple sentence is a basic sentence that expresses a complete thought. It contains: A subject , A verb , A complete thought .Ex. The train was late. Mary and Maggie took the bus.

What is a compound sentence?

As we mention in our guide on how to write better sentences, compound sentences combine two or more independent clauses. The key here is independent clauses, which are clauses that can each stand alone as a separate sentence. Essentially, a compound sentence brings together individual, related sentences as one. Compound sentences are easy to identify because they usually use a coordinating conjunction, which you may remember as FANBOYS: for, and, nor, but, or, yet, and so. However, compound sentences can also use a semicolon to connect two clauses, in which case no conjunction is necessary. Let's look at some compound sentence examples to see how they work.

Compound sentence examples.

Below are two simple complete sentences, each with its own subject and verb: I have a pet iguana. His name is Fluffy. To combine them into a compound sentence, we simply add a comma plus the coordinating conjunction and: I have a pet iguana, and his name is Fluffy.Alternatively, we can make a compound sentence by adding only a semicolon, and the sentence will still be correct: I have a pet iguana; his name is Fluffy.Although they're talking about the same topic, the subject of each independent clause is different: The first clause's subject is I, and the second one's subject is name. That's part of what makes them independent, and a sentence is considered compound only when it consists of independent clauses. For example, the sentence below is not a compound sentence: I have a pet iguana whose name is Fluffy. To be a compound sentence, it needs at least two subjects and two verbs. If both independent clauses use the same subject, it must be stated twice, as in the quote below, for the sentence to be compound: "I alone cannot change the world, but I can cast a stone across the water to create many ripples." —Mother Teresa

Be careful of sentences with only two subjects or only two verbs—these are not the same as compound sentences. The following sentence is not a compound sentence, because there is only one subject (I) even though there are two verbs (chew and study), and because what comes after the conjunction and is not an independent clause: I came here to chew bubblegum and study grammar. However, you can turn this sentence into

a compound sentence by adding another independent clause with a second subject: I came here to chew bubble gum and study grammar, but I'm all out of gum.

Commas and other punctuation in compound sentences: When creating compound sentences, there are two punctuation rules to keep in mind: Place a comma before the coordinating conjunction. If you're not using a coordinating conjunction, place a semicolon between the clauses. As always, you use a lowercase letter to start the second independent clause. Since compound sentences are a single sentence, only the first letter of the first clause is capitalized. Mastering these punctuation rules is crucial for creating compound sentences. Without them, your sentence becomes a dreaded run-on sentence. In writing, run-on sentences are not only grammatically incorrect but also difficult for your reader to understand. To avoid both run-on sentences and confusingly long compound sentences, try to limit the number of clauses in a sentence to two or three. In situations when you need more than three clauses, keep them as short as possible by removing unnecessary words. Remember, short sentences are easier to understand and give your writing a faster pace.

Compound vs. complex sentences

It's easy to get compound sentences confused with complex sentences; both use two or more clauses in a single sentence. The most significant difference, however, is the type of clauses they use. Compound sentences use two or more independent clauses. I am working now, but we will eat later. Complex sentences combine independent clauses with subordinate clauses, also known as dependent clauses.

Because I am working now, we will eat later. In this example, because I am working now is the subordinate clause, and we will eat later is the independent clause. The clue is the word because, which is a subordinating conjunction. Words like because, if, whenever, and since—as well as certain prepositions like after and before—all act as subordinating conjunctions. Their job is to connect subordinate clauses to independent clauses. Just by adding a subordinating conjunction, you can turn an independent clause into a subordinating clause. I am working now alone is an independent clause, but with because in front, it becomes a subordinating clause. Be careful, though, because a sentence can be both complex and compound at the same time! A complex-compound sentence occurs when a single sentence has at least two independent clauses and at least one subordinate clause. After I got home from work, my friends invited me out, and I left my apartment again. In this example, after I got home from work is the subordinate clause (you can tell because the word after appears at the front). Both my friends invited me out and I left my apartment again are independent clauses, joined by the coordinating conjunction and. Put all three clauses

together with the proper punctuation and you have a perfectly correct complex-compound sentence.

In conclusion, a compound sentence is a sentence that usually joins two independent clauses using a coordinating conjunction such as and or but. This is ideal for combining two or more independent but related sentences into one unified sentence. Complex sentences speed up your writing and combine related ideas, but they also have a few more rules than standard sentences. This quick guide will show you how to use them correctly to add something to your writing.

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